

LOW VELOCITY IMPACT RESPONSE OF ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING TI-6AL-4V SANDWICH PANELS WITH LATTICE

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ABSTRACT

The selective laser melting (SLM) technique has great potential application in aviation field. And numerous airplane structures, such as sandwich panels made by SLM, need to withstand unpredictable impact load. In this work, sandwich structures and lattice cores with FCC and BCC were made from TC4 and manufactured by SLM. The failure response of those four different structures subjected to low velocity impact was investigated. Low velocity tests were performed on mass drop testing machine. It is found that structures with BCC has the better resistance to the low velocity impact compared with the FCC structures, while the FCC structures have a higher energy absorption capability. In addition to experimental testing, ABAQUS software was used to develop the three-dimensional finite model of sandwich panels-impactor system. The numerical results were validated compared with the experimental tests.

1 Introduction

Additive manufacturing selective laser melting (AM-SLM) are potential to be widely used in aircraft structural components [1-3]. Compared with the traditional manufacturing method, the selective laser melting (SLM) technology has the advantages of increasing material utilization, shortening the processing period, and reducing the structure weight. It will be widely used in aviation structure in the future. In addition, sandwich structure design is widely used in aerospace, automobile transportation, construction and other industries of structural components of the lightweight application [4-6]. These structures include a relatively low-stiffness core sandwiched between two rigid shells. The sandwich structures are designed to protect of the backing structure from the unwanted impact and to ensure structural integrity.

There have been apparently numerous experimental and numerical investigations and reviews in the literature on impact loading responses of the sandwich structures with periodic cellular cores fabricated by SLM. Zuhail [7] used the implicit and explicit non-linear finite element code to develop the lattice models and demonstrated that a rate-independent load-deflection model of the unit cell layers could be used in a simple multi degree of freedom model to represent the impact behavior of a multi-layer specimen. By designing and printing lattice truss structures fabricated by SLM, Yazdani [8] conducted the low-velocity impact tests to determine their dynamic energy absorption and multi-hit capabilities. It is found that the core topology and geometrical parameters have significant effects on failure mechanism and energy absorption of sandwich structures. Employing a homogenized continuum constitutive model, Jacob [9] replicated the deformation response of the lattice core without requiring explicit representation

of the geometric features. Mines [10] explored the low-velocity drop-weight-impact behavior of a SLM TC4 BCC lattice structure with carbon fiber reinforced plastic skins. He determined that the impact performance of the TC4 is competitive with aluminum honeycomb. Amer [11] investigated the performance of three cellular core designs under low energy impact as sandwich structures, and he focused on correlation between the impact energy absorption of the cellular structures with the quasi-static mechanical properties.

The main objective of this research is to study the low velocity impact response of sandwich panels with BCC and FCC lattice manufactured by SLM. Failure mode and impact response were studied and the numerical finite element models were built to analyze the lattice sandwich structures under impact loading.

2 Experimental study

2.1 Design of sandwich structures

FCC and BCC lattice structures were designed and used in the TC4 sandwich panels, and the unit cells of those two structures are shown in Fig.1. The TC4 sandwich panels with the lattice in the middle and covered by 0.5mm thick sheets in both sides. Each sandwich panel and lattice cores consists of 1 unit cell the Z-direction (vertical), 20 unit cells copied in the X-direction and 30 unit cells copied in the Y-direction. The unit cell is a cube of 5mm edge and the radius of the strut circular cross-sections is 0.5 mm. Hence, the size of sandwich panels is 150mm×100mm×7mm and that of the lattice cores is 150mm×100mm×5mm. The specimens of the sandwich panels and lattice cores are shown in Fig.2 and Fig.3 respectively.

Figure 1 Unit cell design

(a) FCC sandwich

(b) BCC sandwich

Figure 2 TC4 sandwich panels with lattice

(a) FCC lattice

(b) BCC lattice

Figure 3 Lattice cores

2.2 Experimental set-up

The drop-weight impact testing was performed on an instrumented CEAST 9350. And the diameter of the hemispherical impactor is 16 mm. In order to prevent the warping at the boundary of the specimen, some adjustments on the ASTM D 7136 standard were made. The mass block was introduced and shown in Fig.4. In Fig.4, a BCC sandwich panel was placed on the support plate, and ready for impact testing.

Figure 4 Specimen and supporting system ready for testing

2.3 Experimental results

Six sandwich panels and six lattice cores were fabricated and tested under low-velocity impacts at the room temperature. Table 1 shows the impact energy levels that were used for each specimen along with the corresponding drop mass.

The contact force-displacement curves at different energies for sandwich panels and lattice cores are shown in Fig.5(a) and Fig.5(b) respectively. In Fig.5 (a), the initial non-linearity of the curve was caused by the damage of the upper skin, and the reduction of the maximum load was related to the perforation process. The BCC structure shows higher performance load as compared with FCC structure under 124.3J impact energy. That can also be observed in Fig.5(b) when specimens were subjected to impact energy of 13.8J and 21.6J. When the impact energy is 169.2J, there is less difference between those two sandwich panels. This is attributed to the fact that the overall response is mostly dominated by the skin failure behavior. However, when the impact energy is 86.3J, the contact force of BCC sandwich structure is 3.1% lower than that of the FCC sandwich. And at three impact energy levels, the BCC sandwich

always shows the lack of ductility in the core during the perforation.

Design	Panel ID	Drop mass (kg)	Energy level (J)
Sandwich panels with BCC	Sbcc-3#	16.27	86.3
	Sbcc-1#		124.3
	Sbcc-2#		169.2
Sandwich panels with FCC	Sfcc-3#	16.27	86.3
	Sfcc-1#		124.3
	Sfcc-2#		169.2
Lattice cores with BCC	Cbcc-1#	6.797	13.8
	Cbcc-2#		21.6
	Cbcc-3#		31.1
Lattice cores with FCC	Cfcc-1#	6.797	7.8
	Cfcc-2#		13.8
	Cfcc-3#		21.6

Table 1 Impact energy levels for each specimen

Figure 5 Force-displacement curves

Fig.6 (a) and Fig.6 (b) present the experimental results for the energy-time history for sandwich panels and lattice cores respectively. In the energy absorption-time history, the amount of absorbed and returned energies can be observed. The absorbed energy is the energy mostly dissipated by various failure mechanisms such as creaking and perforation. The returned energy is the elastic energy. At the same impact energy, the energy observed by the two configurations of the sandwich panels were almost the same, which can be seen in Fig.6 (a). However, the lattice cores with FCC provided a 45% to 52% higher energy absorption than that of BCC under the same impact energy, which can be seen in Fig.6 (b). It should be noted that the core with BCC is the preferred core, in terms of energy absorption, for the sandwich panel subjected to a specific impact energy.

Figure 6 Energy absorption-time history

The top view of FCC sandwich and BCC sandwich post impact are shown in Fig.7 and Fig.8 respectively. For both structures, with the increase of impact energy, the damage diameter of the upper sheet increased. And cracks appeared on the upper sheet of all specimens. The damage of sandwich panels with FCC and BCC was almost the same at the same impact energy. Damage of lattice cores with FCC and BCC is shown in Fig.9 and Fig.10 respectively. It should be noted that there was no damage for the lattice core with FCC at 7.8J and BCC at 13.8J. The fracture always occurred near the strut junction. However, it can be seen from Fig.9 (b), the fracture occurred in the middle of the strut. This phenomenon may be caused by manufacturing defects. When the impact energy reached 31.1J, the lattice core with BCC was completely penetrated by the impactor.

(a) 86.3J (b) 124.3J (c) 169.2J

Figure 7 The damage of FCC sandwich under different impact energies

(a) 86.3J (b) 124.3J (c) 169.2J

Figure 8 The damage of BCC sandwich under different impact energies

(a) 13.8J

(b) 21.6J

Figure 9 The damage of lattice cores with FCC under different impact energy

(a) 21.6J

(b) 31.1J

Figure 10 The damage of lattice cores with BCC under different impact energy

3. Numerical simulation

ABAQUS software was used to simulate the low velocity impact tests. The impactor was modeled as a rigid body with one degree of freedom in the impact direction, and the mass block was modeled as an infinite mass discrete rigid body which was completely fixed. The lattice cores were explicitly modeled with tetrahedral elements and the skin of the sandwich structure were modeled with hexahedral elements, which are shown in Fig.11(a). In order to improve the computational efficiency, only quarter of specimens was developed by finite element method and the mesh of the impact region was locally refined. In Fig.11(b), the geometrical details of impactor are shown (radius of 8 mm and length of 16 mm).

(a) Specimen

(b) Impactor

Figure 11 Finite element models

The Johnson-Cook material model and Johnson-Cook failure model were used in numerical

simulation. The Johnson-Cook flow stress model is given as

$$\sigma = [A + B\varepsilon^n] \left[1 + C \ln \left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon}}{\dot{\varepsilon}_0} \right) \right] [1 - (T^*)^m] \quad (1)$$

where ε , $\dot{\varepsilon}$, $\dot{\varepsilon}_0$ and T^* are, respectively, the effective plastic strain, strain rate, reference strain rate and nondimensional temperature; A, B, n, c, and m are the model parameters.

The strain at fracture is defines as

$$\varepsilon_f = [D_1 + D_2 \exp(D_3 \sigma^*)] \left[1 + D_4 \ln \left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon}}{\dot{\varepsilon}_0} \right) \right] [1 + D_5 T^*] \quad (2)$$

where σ^* is the ratio of the pressure to the effective stress. D_1, D_2, D_3, D_4 and D_5 are the model parameters.

The reference mechanical properties of the TC4 material [12] is listed in Table 2

Density $\rho/(\text{Kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3})$	Elastic modulus E/GPa	Poisson's ratio ν	T_{melt}/K	A/MPa
4430	135	0.33	1878	1060
B/MPa	n	C	m	$\dot{\varepsilon}$
1090	0.884	0.0117	1.1	4×10^{-4}
D_1	D_2	D_3	D_4	D_5
-0.09	0.27	0.48	0.014	3.87

Table 2 The reference mechanical properties of the TC4 material

Assuming that the connection between the core and skin was perfect [13]. The general contact was adopted between the impactor, mass block and sandwich panels. In addition, the friction effect between the components was taken into account. The friction coefficient of the contact surface was 0.1[14].

The force-displacement curves of experimental tests of sandwich panels with FCC are compared to their respective curves derived from the numerical analysis in Fig.12. From Fig.12, it can be observed that the calculated peak load is higher and the displacement after the peak of contact force is lower than the experimental ones. That is contributed to the assumption that the connection between the core and skin is prefect. Fig.13 shows the simulated damage of the lattice core with BCC post impact of 31.1J. The BCC structure was completely penetrated, which can also be seen in Fig.10 (b). Fig.12 and Fig.13 present an overall good correlation between the experimental and numerical finite element models, indicating that the numerical model is capable of predicting the failure of the sandwich panels with lattice.

Figure 12 Numerical and experimental force-displacement curves for specimens subjected to impact energy of 86.3J and 124.3J

Figure 13 Simulated damage of the lattice core with BCC post impact of 31.1J

4. Conclusion

In this paper, the low-velocity impact response of additive manufacturing ti-6al-4v sandwich panels with lattice is studied. The contact force-displacement curves and energy absorption-time history are obtained. Also, numerical simulations based on ABAQUS are conducted. The conclusions are as follows:

1. The sandwich panels with BCC has better resistance to the low velocity impact.
2. The lattice cores with FCC provided a 45% to 52% higher energy absorption than that of BCC under the same impact energy
3. The numerical results agree well with the experimental ones.

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